

SPLITTING OF RATIONAL PRIMES IN THE RING OF ALGEBRAIC INTEGERS

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Abstract:

We know that the primes in $\mathbb{Z}$ (hereafter referred as rational primes) are irreducible in $\mathbb{Z}$ i.e they don't have proper factorization. If R is any factorization domain such that $\mathbb{Z}$ is properly contained in R then are these rational primes also irreducible in R ? The answer to this question in general is No. For example, 2 is prime in $\mathbb{Z}$ but 2 is not prime in $\mathbb{Z}[i]$ as we can write 2 as: $2 = (1 + i)(1 - i)$ where both $1 + i$ & $1 - i$ are irreducible (rather non units) in $\mathbb{Z}[i]$. In this paper we will see how the rational primes split in the ring of algebraic integers.

Key Words: Algebraic Number Field, Integral Basis, Discriminant & Ramify

1. Introduction:

An Algebraic number field is a subfield of $\mathbb{C}$ (field of complex numbers) of the form $\mathbb{Q}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n)$, where $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$ are algebraic numbers. Let K be an algebraic number field. A basis for $\mathcal{O}_K$ is called an integral basis for K . Let $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ be an integral basis for K . Then $D(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n)$ is called the discriminant of K and is denoted by $d(K)$ or d_K . Moreover, in any algebraic number field K , every proper integral ideal of $\mathcal{O}_K$ can be expressed uniquely up to order as a product of prime ideals. Let p be a rational prime. Suppose $\langle p \rangle$ factors in $\mathcal{O}_K$ as $\langle p \rangle = P_1^{e_1} P_2^{e_2} \dots P_g^{e_g}$, where $P_1, P_2, \dots, P_g$ are distinct prime ideals of $\mathcal{O}_K$ lying above p where, $e_i = e_K(P_i)$; $i = 1, 2, \dots, g$. If $e_i > 1$ for some $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, g\}$ then p is said to be ramify in K .

Definition 1.1: (Basis of an Ideal)

Let K be an algebraic number field of degree n . Let I be a nonzero ideal of $\mathcal{O}_K$. If $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ is a set of elements of I such that every element $\beta \in I$ can be expressed uniquely in the form as $\beta = x_1\alpha_1 + x_2\alpha_2 + \dots + x_n\alpha_n$ where $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{Z}$ then $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ is called a basis for the ideal I .

Definition 1.2: (Discriminant of n Elements in an Algebraic Number Field of Degree n)

Let K be an algebraic number field of degree n . Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$ be n elements of the field K . Let σ_k ; $1 \leq k \leq n$ denote the n distinct monomorphisms from K to $\mathbb{C}$. For $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ let $\alpha_i^{(1)} = \sigma_1(\alpha_i) = \alpha_i$, $\alpha_i^{(2)} = \sigma_2(\alpha_i)$, $\dots$, $\alpha_i^{(n)} = \sigma_n(\alpha_i)$ denote the conjugate of α_i relative to K . Then the discriminant of $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ is

$$D(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n) = \left(\det \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1^{(1)} & \dots & \alpha_n^{(1)} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \alpha_1^{(n)} & \dots & \alpha_n^{(n)} \end{bmatrix} \right)^2$$

Definition 1.3: (Discriminant of an Ideal)

Let K be an algebraic number field of degree n . Let I be a nonzero ideal of $\mathcal{O}_K$. Let $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ be a basis of I . Then the discriminant $D(I)$ of the ideal I is the nonzero integer given by $D(I) = D(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n)$.

Definition 1.4: (Index of θ)

Let K be an algebraic number field of degree n . Let $\theta \in K$ be such that $K = \mathbb{Q}(\theta)$. Then the index of θ , denoted by $\text{ind}(\theta)$ is the positive integer given by $D(\theta) = D(1, \theta, \theta^2, \dots, \theta^{n-1}) = (\text{ind}(\theta))^2 d(K)$. Note that if $D(\theta)$ is square free then $\text{ind}(\theta) = 1$ and $D(\theta) = d(K)$. Thus $\{1, \theta, \theta^2, \dots, \theta^{n-1}\}$ is an integral basis for K .

2. Main Section:

Let θ be a root of $x^4 + x + 1 = 0$. Let $f(x) = x^4 + x + 1$, is monic and irreducible over $\mathbb{Z}$. $[K:\mathbb{Q}] = 4$.

Theorem 2.1:

Let a, b be integers such that $x^4 + ax + b$ is irreducible over $\mathbb{Z}$. Let θ be a root of $x^4 + ax + b$ so that $K = \mathbb{Q}(\theta)$ is a quartic field and $\theta \in \mathcal{O}_K$. Then, $D(\theta) = -27a^4 + 256b^3$

As $a = b = 1$. Thus, $D(\theta) = -27 + 256 = 229$. Since $D(\theta)$ is square free. Therefore, $d_K = D(\theta)$.

Hence $\{1, \theta, \theta^2, \theta^3\}$ is an integral basis of K .

Theorem 2.2:

Let K be an algebraic number field with $[K:\mathbb{Q}] = n$. Let p be a rational prime. Suppose $\langle p \rangle$ factors in $\mathcal{O}_K$ as $\langle p \rangle = P_1^{e_1} P_2^{e_2} \dots P_g^{e_g}$, where $P_1, P_2, \dots, P_g$ are distinct prime ideals of $\mathcal{O}_K$. Suppose that f_i is the inertial degree of P_i in K . Then, $e_1 f_1 + e_2 f_2 + \dots + e_g f_g = n$

Note that $g \leq n$

In present case, $g \leq 4$

If $g = 4: e_1 f_1 + e_2 f_2 + e_3 f_3 + e_4 f_4 = 4$
 i.e. $e_1 = f_1 = e_2 = f_2 = e_3 = f_3 = e_4 = f_4 = 1$
 Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2 P_3 P_4$; $N(P_i) = p$
 If $g = 3: e_1 f_1 + e_2 f_2 + e_3 f_3 = 4$
 Wlog, assume that $e_1 f_1 = 2$ and $e_2 f_2 = e_3 f_3 = 1$
 $(e_1, f_1) = (1, 2), (2, 1)$ and $e_2 = f_2 = e_3 = f_3 = 1$
 Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2 P_3$; $N(P_1) = p^2$, $N(P_2) = N(P_3) = p$
 Or
 $\langle p \rangle = P_1^2 P_2 P_3$; $N(P_1) = N(P_2) = N(P_3) = p$
 If $g = 2: e_1 f_1 + e_2 f_2 = 4$
 $(e_1, f_1) = (1, 2), (2, 1)$ and $(e_2, f_2) = (1, 2), (2, 1)$
 Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2$; $N(P_1) = p^2 = N(P_2)$
 Or
 $\langle p \rangle = P_1^2 P_2$; $N(P_1) = p$, $N(P_2) = p^2$
 Or
 $\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2^2$; $N(P_2) = p$, $N(P_1) = p^2$
 Or
 $\langle p \rangle = P_1^2 P_2^2$; $N(P_1) = N(P_2) = p$
 Wlog, assume that $(e_1, f_1) = 3$ and $(e_2, f_2) = 1$
 $(e_1, f_1) = (1, 3), (3, 1)$ and $e_2 = f_2 = 1$
 Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2$; $N(P_1) = p^3$, $N(P_2) = p$
 Or
 $\langle p \rangle = P_1^3 P_2$; $N(P_1) = N(P_2) = p$
 If $g = 1: e_1 f_1 = 4$
 $(e_1, f_1) = (1, 4), (4, 1)$
 Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1$; $N(P_1) = p^4$
 Or
 $\langle p \rangle = P_1^4$; $N(P_1) = p$
 Let us see how rational primes split in O_K

Theorem 2.3:

Let $K = Q(\theta)$ be an algebraic number field of degree n such that $O_K = Z[\theta]$. Let p be a rational prime, let $f(x) = \text{irr}_{Q\theta} \in Z[x]$. Let $\bar{}$ denote the natural map: $Z[x] \rightarrow Z_p[x]$ where $Z_p = Z/pZ$. Let $\bar{f}(x) = g_1^{e_1}(x) g_2^{e_2}(x) \dots g_r^{e_r}(x)$ where $g_i(x)$ are distinct monic irreducibles in $Z_p[x]$, $1 \leq i \leq r$ and $e_1, e_2, \dots, e_r$ are positive integers. For $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$, let $f_i(x)$ be any monic polynomial of $Z[x]$ such that $\bar{f}_i = g_i$. Set $P_i = \langle p, f_i(\theta) \rangle$; $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$. Then $P_1, P_2, \dots, P_r$ are distinct prime ideals of O_K with $\langle p \rangle = P_1^{e_1} P_2^{e_2} \dots P_r^{e_r}$ and $N(P_i) = p^{\text{deg } f_i}$; $1 \leq i \leq r$.

For $p = 2$, Since $x^4 + x + 1$ is irreducible over Z_2 .

Set $P = \langle 2, \theta^4 + \theta + 1 \rangle$ but $\theta^4 + \theta + 1 = 0$

Thus $P = \langle 2 \rangle$; $N(P) = 16$ and 2 will remain as prime in O_K

For $p = 3$, $x^4 + x + 1 = (x - 1)(x^3 + x^2 + x + 2)$ over $Z_3[x]$ and $x^3 + x^2 + x + 2$ is irreducible over Z_3

Set $P_1 = \langle 3, \theta - 1 \rangle$; $N(P_1) = 3$

Set $P_2 = \langle 3, \theta^3 + \theta^2 + \theta + 2 \rangle$; $N(P_2) = 27$

Thus, $\langle 3 \rangle = P_1 P_2$

For $p = 5$, $x^4 + x + 1 = (x - 3)(x^3 + 3x^2 + 4x + 3)$ over $Z_5[x]$ and $x^3 + 3x^2 + 4x + 3$ is irreducible over Z_5

Set $P_1 = \langle 5, \theta - 3 \rangle$; $N(P_1) = 5$

Set $P_2 = \langle 5, \theta^3 + 3\theta^2 + 4\theta + 3 \rangle$; $N(P_2) = 125$

Thus $\langle 5 \rangle = P_1 P_2$

Theorem 2.4:

Let K be an algebraic number field. Then the rational prime ramifies in K iff p divides d_K

As $d_K = 229$ which is a rational prime i.e. $p = 229$ ramifies in O_K

For $p = 229$, $x^4 + x + 1 = (x - 75)^2 (x^2 + 150x + 158)$ over $Z_{229}[x]$ and $x^2 + 150x + 158$ is irreducible over Z_{229}

Set $P_1 = \langle 229, \theta - 75 \rangle$; $N(P_1) = 229$

Set $P_2 = \langle 229, \theta^2 + 150\theta + 158 \rangle$; $N(P_2) = (229)^2$

Thus $\langle 229 \rangle = P_1^2 P_2$

3. References:

1. Saban Alaca and Kenneth S. Williams, *Introductory Algebraic Number Theory*, Cambridge University Press.